

Size	Neon (LUPS)	Taichi (LUPS)	Speedup
4096×1024	33346.73	29304.42	1.14
8192×2048	33740.24	33979.88	0.99
16384×4096	34001.84	34729.78	0.98
32768×8192	206079.33	206127	0.999

Neon’s speedup over Taichi [11] on the 2D Kármán Vortex Street LBM application using LUPS metric. Experiments were run on a single GPU of a DGX A100 server.

Percentage of memory transfer that is overlapped with computation on the Poisson solver using different OCC options offered by Neon. Note that NoOCC causes 0% of the communication to overlap with computation and thus it is discarded.